

Spectroscopy, electrochemistry and biocidal activity of amino acid Schiff base metal complexes

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Abstract : Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and VO^{II} Schiff base complexes derived from indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ind) and amino acids viz. L-alanine (ala), L-phenylalanine (pala) and L-histidine (his) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic absorption and EPR (at room temperature and at 77 K) spectroscopic techniques. The electrochemical properties of Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a well-defined quasireversible redox wave attributed to one electron transfer process. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes were screened for their biocidal activities *in vitro* on common bacteria.

Keywords : Indole-3-carboxaldehyde, cyclic voltammetry, biocidal activity.

Introduction

As part of our systematic study on amino acid Schiff base metal complexes¹⁻³, we now report the synthesis, spectroscopy, electrochemistry and biocidal activities of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and VO^{II} Schiff base complexes derived from indole-3-carboxaldehyde and amino acids, L-alanine (Indala), L-phenylalanine (Indpala) and L-histidine (Indhis). The studies have helped in understanding the coordination environment of Schiff base ligands around the metal ion.

Results and discussion

All the complexes are soluble in methanol, ethanol and DMSO. The general characteristic properties and analytical data of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The observed molar conductances of the complexes in ethanol for $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions at room temperature are consistent with the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes⁴.

IR spectra : Indole-3-carboxaldehyde (Ind) exhibits a strong band at 1634 cm⁻¹ due to the aldehydic group. The strong band appeared in the 1613–1580 cm⁻¹ region for the Schiff bases (in solution) is attributed to the C=N stretching vibration for C=N group due to condensation of aldehyde group of Ind and amino group of amino acid. This band undergoes a shift to lower

frequency to 1600–1560 cm⁻¹ after complexation indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to metal ion⁵. The strong NH stretching frequency band appeared at 3166 cm⁻¹ for the free ligand and the Schiff base is unaltered in the metal complexes clearly demonstrates the non involvement of NH group in coordination with metal ion. The bands appearing at 1625–1610 cm⁻¹ region is assigned to imidazole ring $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibration shifted to lower frequency by 5–10 cm⁻¹ indicating the participation of the imidazole ring nitrogen in chelation. A very strong band in the 1625–1595 cm⁻¹ range and the band in the 1396–1367 cm⁻¹ region for the studied complexes is typical for the asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of the coordinated carboxylate group, confirms the coordination of the Schiff base through the carboxylate oxygen⁵. In the low frequency region, the band observed for the complexes in the 468–420 cm⁻¹ region is attributed to (M–O) and in the 540–530 cm⁻¹ region to (M–N) stretching⁶. To summarize, the IR data suggest that the metal ion is bound to the Schiff base through the imino nitrogen and carboxylate oxygen in the M^{II}-Indala/Indpala systems. In the M^{II}-Indhis system the Schiff base ligand coordinates the metal ion in a tridentate mode via imino-N, carboxylate-O and imidazole-N atoms. The vanadyl complexes show an additional band at 950 cm⁻¹ is due to

Table 1. Elemental analysis, molar conductance and melting point of the Schiff base metal complexes

Compd.	Color	Empirical formula	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)				Conduc. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
				M	C	H	N		
CuL ₂	Brown	CuC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄	49	12.79 (12.86)	58.37 (58.31)	4.47 (4.45)	11.29 (11.33)	4.26	218
NiL ₂	Green	NiC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄	52	11.95 (12.00)	58.92 (58.89)	4.51 (4.49)	11.40 (11.45)	3.94	205
ZnL ₂ (2H ₂ O)	White	ZnC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ (2H ₂ O)	42	12.21 (12.29)	54.18 (54.16)	4.93 (4.89)	10.50 (10.53)	3.79	221
CoL ₂ (2H ₂ O)	Red	CoC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ (2H ₂ O)	55	11.15 (11.21)	54.86 (54.83)	4.96 (4.95)	10.60 (10.66)	4.14	209.
MnL ₂ (2H ₂ O)	Brown	MnC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄ (2H ₂ O)	61	10.45 (10.53)	55.28 (55.25)	4.91 (4.98)	10.72 (10.74)	3.92	211
VOL ₂	Green	VOC ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄	50	10.51 (10.58)	59.87 (59.84)	4.61 (4.57)	11.57 (11.63)	3.74	215
CuL' ₂	Brown	CuC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄	54	9.78 (9.83)	66.86 (66.84)	4.64 (4.60)	8.61 (8.66)	2.64	205
NiL' ₂	Green	NiC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄	49	9.11 (9.15)	67.38 (67.35)	4.71 (4.67)	8.71 (8.73)	2.73	221
ZnL'' ₂ (2H ₂ O)	White	ZnC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ (2H ₂ O)	45	9.51 (9.55)	63.09 (63.15)	4.91 (4.97)	8.11 (8.18)	2.61	207
CoL'' ₂ (2H ₂ O)	Pink	CoC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ (2H ₂ O)	42	8.61 (8.69)	63.80 (63.75)	5.07 (5.01)	8.21 (8.26)	2.39	211
MnL'' ₂ (2H ₂ O)	Brown	MnC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄ (2H ₂ O)	55	8.09 (8.15)	64.13 (64.16)	5.04 (5.07)	8.25 (8.31)	2.26	219
VOL'' ₂	Green	VOC ₃₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₄	42	7.99 (8.03)	68.17 (68.21)	4.73 (4.69)	8.76 (8.83)	2.63	213
CuL''' ₂	Brown	CuC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	43	10.11 (10.14)	57.54 (57.49)	4.17 (4.15)	17.81 (17.88)	3.61	218
NiL''' ₂	Green	NiC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	48	9.41 (9.44)	57.96 (57.93)	4.21 (4.18)	17.98 (18.02)	2.42	210
ZnL''' ₂	White	ZnC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	45	10.37 (10.40)	57.36 (57.32)	4.17 (4.14)	17.81 (17.83)	2.94	219
CoL''' ₂	Pink	CoC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	42	9.44 (9.48)	57.85 (57.91)	4.14 (4.18)	17.94 (18.01)	3.19	206
MnL''' ₂	Brown	MnC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	55	8.81 (8.89)	58.34 (58.29)	4.26 (4.20)	18.05 (18.13)	3.82	217
VOL''' ₂	Green	VOC ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₄	52	8.21 (8.30)	58.71 (58.67)	4.25 (4.23)	18.19 (18.25)	2.86	220

Calculated values are given in parentheses; L' = Indala; L'' = Indpala; L''' = Indhis.

the V=O frequency. The IR spectrum of Co^{II} and Mn^{II}-Indala/Indpala complexes show a broad band in the 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ region, confirms the presence of water molecules coordinated to the metal ion.

Electronic absorption spectra and magnetic measurements : The geometry of the Schiff base metal complexes is obtained with the help of electronic absorption and magnetic measurements. The electronic absorption spectral data of the Schiff base metal complexes are given in Table 2, which includes the absorption regions, band assignments and the proposed geometry of the complexes. These values are comparable with other reported values⁷⁻⁹.

ESR spectra : The X-band ESR spectrum of Cu^{II}-Indala complex in MeCN solution measured at 300 and 77 K. The 300 K spectrum shows an isotropic pattern for Cu^{II} in solution is due to the tumbling motion of the molecules. But the spectrum for the frozen solution shows anisotropic pattern. In the Cu^{II}-Indala complex, the unpaired electron lies in the orbital having ²B_{1g} as the ground state, which has g values in the ratio g_{||} > g_⊥ > 2. From the observed values it is clear that the

Fig. 1. Structure of Schiff base ligands.

reported ratio and the ESR parameters of the complex coincide well, which suggests that the complex has square planar geometry and the system is axially symmetric¹⁰. Furthermore, this conclusion is supported by the fact that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the d_{x²-y²} orbital. The molecular orbital coefficients σ -bonding (α^2) and π -bonding (β^2) are calculated¹¹. From Table 3, it is clear that in-plane σ -bonding (0.47) is more covalent than in-plane π -bonding (0.87). The α^2 value

Table 2. Electronic absorption and IR spectral data of the Schiff base metal complexes at 300 K

Complex	Absorption λ_{\max} (in cm^{-1})	Band assignments	Geometry	$\nu(\text{M-O})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{M-N})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{C=N})$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{COO}^-)_s$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu(\text{COO}^-)_{as}$ (cm^{-1})
Cu ^{II} -Indala	16893	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$	Square	429	530	1576	1392	1613
Cu ^{II} -Indpala	14000	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$	planar	434	522	1579	1391	1611
	10900	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$						
Cu ^{II} -Indhis	11500-13600	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$	Distorted octahedral	463	518	1581	1390	1608
Co ^{II} -Indala	9552-9918	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$						
Co ^{II} -Indpala	14347-14964	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	Octahedral	429	532	1576	1389	1614
Co ^{II} -Indhis	17403-18707	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$		431	548	1584	1386	1611
	39088-38861	CT		429	539	1581	1392	1609
Ni ^{II} -Indala	15854-16567	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$	Square	429	532	1578	1386	1608
Ni ^{II} -Indpala	19989-21899	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$	planar	428	539	1582	1386	1609
	28608-30172	CT						
Ni ^{II} -Indhis	15400	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	Octahedral	431	542	1584	1391	1609
VO ^{II} -Indala	19600, 13400	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$	Square	428	482	1612	1356	1614
VO ^{II} -Indpala		${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$	pyramidal	433	472	1613	1347	1620
VO ^{II} -Indhis				428	482	1589	1382	1609

*All the oxovanadium complexes shows an additional peak at 960-978 cm^{-1} .

indicates that the system is completely covalent. The parameter G has been calculated by $G = (g_{\parallel} - g_e) / (g_{\perp} - g_e)$. A value of G greater than four ($G = 6.83$) indicates that considerable exchange interaction is absent. No band corresponding to $M_s = \pm 2$ transition was observed in the spectrum ruling out any Cu-Cu interactions¹¹.

The room temperature (300 K) spectrum of vanadyl complex recorded in DMSO solution contains a typical eight line pattern which shows that a single vanadium is present in the molecule. In the frozen solid state (77 K), the spectrum shows 16-lines hyperfine splitting, characteristic of an interaction between the electron and the vanadium nuclear spin. The observed parameters (Table 3) indicate that the unpaired electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital with square-pyramidal geom-

etry around the VO^{II} chelates. The molecular orbital coefficients calculated indicate that the in-plane σ -bonding is more covalent than the in-plane π -bonding.

Electrochemistry : The electrochemical behaviours of the Cu^{II} complexes were examined by means of cyclic voltammetry in DMSO (Table 4). Cu^{II}-Indala exhibits a well-defined quasireversible redox wave Cu^{II}/Cu^I attributed to one electron transfer process with E_{pc} at -0.90 V and E_{pa} at -0.13 V. For this couple, the difference between the cathodic and anodic peak potentials (ΔE_p) is of the order 0.77 V, a large peak-to-peak separation in comparison to Nernstian value (59 mV) observed for one electron transfer couple. Large peak width for one electron couple Cu^{II} \rightarrow Cu^I is fairly common observation and is due to the reorganization of the coordination sphere during the electron transfer pro-

Table 3. The spin Hamiltonian parameters of Cu^{II} and VO^{II} Schiff base complexes in DMSO at 300 and 77 K

Complex	Hyperfine constant $\times 10^{-4}$ (cm^{-1})							
	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{iso}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	α^2	β^2
Cu-Indala	145	25	65	2.26	2.04	2.11	0.69	0.95
Cu-Indpala	132	27	62	2.30	2.07	2.14	0.71	0.98
Cu-Indhis	118	24	55	2.36	2.09	2.18	0.74	0.98
VO-Indala	174	76	108	1.96	1.94	1.95	0.61	0.93
VO-Indpala	182	79	113	1.98	1.96	1.97	0.69	0.97
VO-Indhis	179	75	109	1.95	1.97	1.96	0.75	0.84

Table 4. Redox potential for Cu^{II} Schiff base complexes in MeCN solution containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ at 300 K

Complex	Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pa} (V)	E _{pc} (V)	ΔE _p	I _{pa} (μA)	I _{pc} (μA)	I _{pc} /I _{pa}
Cu-Indala	50	-0.13	-0.90	0.77	-18.17	17.50	0.96
Cu-Indpala	50	-0.09	-0.69	0.60	-17.21	16.72	0.97
Cu-Indhis	50	-0.01	-0.53	0.52	-14.66	14.81	1.01

cess¹². The ratio of cathodic to anodic peak currents I_{pc}/I_{pa} is less than unity (0.96). The criterion for reversibility of the process is satisfied as on increasing the scan rate and the voltammogram does not show any significant change.

Biocidal activities : The biocidal activities of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes (50 μg per test) *in vitro* were tested against the Gram positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram negative bacteria *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *Strepto coccus sps.*, by the disc diffusion method¹³ using agar as nutrient and ampicillin as a control. The zone of inhibition against the growth of bacteriae for the complexes (Table 5) shows that inhibition zone of

Table 5. Antimicrobial activities of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes (zone formation in mm)

Complexes	<i>S. Aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>Strepto coccus sps.</i>
Ampicillin	12	10	-	11
Cu ^{II} -Indala	14	11	13	15
Cu ^{II} -Indpala	12	14	19	17
Cu ^{II} -Indhis	11	17	18	19
Ni ^{II} -Indala	17	15	13	12
Ni ^{II} -Indpala	15	16	14	14
Ni ^{II} -Indhis	12	14	17	15

Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes are higher than those of the control (ampicillin). This can be explained by the chelation¹⁴ of the Schiff base with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. The chelation reduces the polarity of the central metal atom, mainly because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the ligand. Also, the normal cell process may be affected by the formation of hydrogen bond, through the azomethine nitrogen atom with the active centers of cell constituents.

Experimental

All chemicals and solvents were obtained from B.D.H. (AnalaR) except indole-3-carboxaldehyde, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine and L-histidine, which were

obtained from Fluka (Puriss). Microanalytical data were performed at RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow. The magnetic, spectral and cyclic voltammetric measurements were carried out as described earlier¹⁻³. The biocidal activities of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base complexes (50 μg per test) *in vitro* were tested against the bacteria by the disc diffusion method¹³ using agar as nutrient and ampicillin as a control.

Synthesis : 5 mmol of the amino acid (20 ml) dissolved in minimum amount of water containing KOH (5 mmol/20 ml) was added dropwise to an ethanolic solution of indole-3-carboxaldehyde (5 mmol; 0.0145 g) in 20 ml, with constant stirring and refluxed for 6 h. The yellow coloration of the solution is the indication of formation of Schiff base. Several attempts to solidify the Schiff bases were failed. To the Schiff base solution (5 mmol/20 ml) appropriate metal chlorides (or) nitrates (5 mmol/10 ml) in minimum amount of water was added and stirred under reflux for 5 h. The solution was evaporated to 5 ml and kept aside. The resulting solid was filtered-off, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure (yield 42–61%). All the complexes were synthesized by the same method.

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